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Review

D_+^* : A risk aware platform agnostic heterogeneous path planner[☆]

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ABSTRACT

This article establishes the novel D_+^* , a risk-aware and platform-agnostic heterogeneous global path planner for robotic navigation in complex environments. The proposed planner addresses a fundamental bottleneck of occupancy-based path planners related to their dependency on accurate and dense maps. More specifically, their performance is highly affected by poorly reconstructed or sparse areas (e.g. holes in the walls or ceilings) leading to faulty generated paths outside the physical boundaries of the 3-dimensional space. As it will be presented, D_+^* addresses this challenge with three novel contributions, integrated into one solution, namely: (a) the proximity risk, (b) the modeling of the unknown space, and (c) the map updates. By adding a risk layer to spaces that are closer to the occupied ones, some holes are filled, and thus the problematic short-cutting through them to the final goal is prevented. The novel established D_+^* also provides safety marginals to the walls and other obstacles, a property that results in paths that do not cut the corners that could potentially disrupt the platform operation. D_+^* has also the capability to model the unknown space as risk-free areas that should keep the paths inside, e.g. in a tunnel environment, and thus heavily reducing the risk of larger shortcuts through openings in the walls. D_+^* is also introducing a dynamic map handling capability that continuously updates with the latest information acquired during the map building process, allowing the planner to use constant map growth and resolve cases of planning over outdated sparser map reconstructions. The proposed path planner is also capable to plan 2D and 3D paths by only changing the input map to a 2D or 3D map and it is independent of the dynamics of the robotic platform. The efficiency of the proposed scheme is experimentally evaluated in multiple real-life experiments where D_+^* is producing successfully proper planned paths, either in 2D in the use case of the Boston dynamics Spot robot or 3D paths in the case of an unmanned areal vehicle in varying and challenging scenarios.

1. Introduction

Robots are becoming more and more common for a large variety of tasks in real-life challenging environments, including but not limited to search and rescue (Agha et al., 2021; Hayat, Yanmaz, Bettstetter, & Brown, 2020; Mishra, Garg, Narang, & Mishra, 2020; San Juan, Santos, & Andújar, 2018; Schedl, Kurmi, & Bimber, 2021), inspection (Zhang, Zhang, & Low, 2021), and delivery (She & Ouyang, 2021). In general, robotic competitions and similar events like the recent DARPA's Sub-Terranean Challenge (DARPA, 2020) have increased the popularity of robotic platforms, their interaction, and their collaborative operation. With the utilization of multiple robotic platforms, large areas can be covered collaboratively, or multiple tasks can be executed simultaneously with increased performance. However, with the increased number of robots, the complexity increases as well, while the overall usability reduces for every robot, a reality that is caused by the utilization of

unique robot-specific software and corresponding settings. One way to simplify the challenge of operating multiple robots is to unify parts of the software independently of the type of platform. Path planning is such an area where a platform-agnostic algorithm could be beneficial and thus in this article we propose a novel D_+^* platform-agnostic global path planner and experimentally evaluate it with the Boston Dynamics (BD) Spot quadruped robot and a quadrotor.

Some path-planning algorithms base their operation on the utilization of environmental characteristics to generate paths in the operational environment. As an example, one can mention the COMPRA framework (Lindqvist, Kanellakis, Mansouri, akbar Agha-mohammadi & Nikolakopoulos, 2021) where the narrow nature of tunnels is utilized to fly towards the deepest point of the tunnel and thus explore it in an efficient way. However, this method works well in tunnels and similar environments, but it is not able to handle junctions and open spaces in

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a good way. For similar reasons, using a heterogeneous path planner, like the herein novel proposed D_+^* that is able to work efficiently in many environments, is a most desired need.

Many path planners utilize an occupancy map (Hornung, Wurm, Bennewitz, Stachniss, & Burgard, 2013; Wang et al., 2021; Xiong, Gao, Wang, Li, & Lin, 2021; Zhang et al., 2021) to plan upon, as for example, RRT*, A*, theta*, D*, and the jump point search (Wu, Xu, Zhen, & Wu, 2019; Zammit & Kampen). However, these planners do rely on a dense occupancy map in order to avoid the problematic situations of generating invalid paths or shortcuts that are planned through obstacles and wall openings. Multiple ways of plugging such holes have been suggested, like filtering (Atapour-Abarghouei & Breckon, 2018) or inflation (Li, Zlatanova, Koopman, Bai, & Diakité, 2018) for example. Filtering can solve many imperfections of a map, however, it can also filter out smaller features, such as small actual openings in the operational environment. Furthermore, inflation of the occupied spaces is a simple solution that creates a safety marginal that forces the path to be planned inside the safe region and thus has some marginal for errors. However, inflation is a hard artificially created boundary that can block a path, where a robot would have been able to go, even though it would be a higher risk passage. Alike these two approaches, risk-aware-based path planners can accept some risks to reach the goal without taking unnecessary risks (Laconte et al., 2021).

Utilizing a risk assessment to plan for a better path is something that has been addressed previously in the scientific literature as in Cuevas, Ramirez, Shames, and Manzić (2021), Huang et al. (2020). However, one of the biggest challenges, when working with risk maps, is how to generate the risk and what to consider as a risk. In many realistic application scenarios, a type of risk that can be considered is the consequences if a crash or failure occurs (Hu, Pang, Dai, & Low, 2020; Primatesta et al., 2017), and then minimizing the consequences of a crash. An alternative method is to utilize offline and online risk maps to plan crash-safe paths as in da Silva Arantes, Toledo, Williams, and Ono (2019) and Primatesta, Guglieri, and Rizzo (2019), while this approach is considering a 2D risk map in open areas to plan their paths. Considering the consequences of a crash is a very good approach to enable good paths, however, it does not aid in actually avoiding a true collision, while for the case of path planning for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) that can move in 3D, the risk assessment and path planning algorithms should utilize all three dimensions when planning a path (Hakobyan, Kim, & Yang, 2019). Risk considerations for safe path planning in a confined environment and by using 3D maneuvering is barely done in the literature. Thus, one of the few works as in Zhou, Pan, Gao, and Shen (2021) utilizes a prediction risk of unknown areas and controls the yaw angle to identify and calculate potential dangers as early as possible. For the case of ground robots, rough and uneven surfaces can be considered as a realistic risk (Ono, Fuchs, Steffy, Maimone, & Yen, 2015; Puck et al., 2020), however, sharp rocks and loose sand that are true risks for ground robots do not constitute real relevant risks for UAVs unless it is so loose that the UAV creates dust out of it. As such, depending on the environment and the utilized robotic platform, different things can be identified as a risk and with a different estimation of their severity impact, while one of the few things that are always dangerous for the robotic operation is the existence of obstacles and the corresponding proximity to the obstacles.

Many path planners try to plan the shortest possible path, either by ensuring that it as a grid search method like the D* style planners or as sample-based planners, like the RRT* that performs pseudo-random guessing of a path and settles for one that is good enough. In this approach, the shortest path around a corner is tangent to the inside corner, but although this is a free space, it is not necessarily safe for a robot to be that close to an obstacle, mainly due to inaccuracies in mapping, state estimation, and path tracking. Thus, one option to generate safe paths is to use model constraints, such in the methods in Tordesillas and How (2021), Tordesillas, Lopez, and How (2019) and Yan F. (2013) when planning. These path planners are able to generate

paths with the knowledge of robot kinematics and ensure that the path is possible to traverse. One of the main disadvantages is the complexity of these planners is the need to know the kinematic model of the robot, which makes it hard to allow for a generalized application of these algorithms between different robots.

Among the platform agnostic planners, one can highlight the Graph-based Exploration Planner 2.0 (Gblanner) Dang, Tranzatto, Khat-tak, Mascarich, Alexis, and Hutter (2020), Kulkarni, Dharmadhikari, Tranzatto, Zimmermann, Reijgwart, De Petris, Nguyen, Khedekar, Pappachristos, Ott, Siegwart, Hutter, and Alexis (2022), which was developed and utilized by team CERBERUS who won the DARPA subter-ranean challenge (DARPA, 2020). Gblanner is a combined exploration and path planning solution that builds a graph through a RRT local planning step. After the graph is built, Dijkstra's algorithm is used to rapidly plan global paths on it. In our work, we will evaluate our planner against Gblanner, which is a state-of-the-art path planning solution.

Thus, the main contribution of this article is the establishment of the novel D_+^* occupancy-based risk-aware, platform-agnostic, heterogeneous global path planner. The novelty of D_+^* stems from the evolution of D*-lite by (1) treating proximity to occupied spaces as risky areas, (2) modeling explicitly unknown areas as a risk, and (3) allowing dynamic 3D map updates for planning. Moreover, D_+^* is a field-hardened global planner that has been extensively tested and evaluated on a quadruped Spot robot and an UAV. D_+^* stands, to the best of the author's knowledge, one of the few global path planners that are able to avoid obstacles by maneuvering in full 3D and considering risks while doing so. At the same time, D_+^* is the first algorithm where these types of risks and path planning methods are used in combination. Finally, the code has also been made open source for the robotics community and is available on GitHub.¹

1.1. Outline

The rest of the article is structured as follows. In Section 2 a complete presentation of the architecture and core components of D_+^* is provided, while in Section 3 the experimental setups for the algorithmic evaluation are explained. In Section 4 the extended experimental evaluation of the suggested scheme is presented, while future work and conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2. D_+^*

The D*-lite (Koenig & Likhachev, 2002) algorithm is able to plan a path on a grid (\mathbb{G}) where it finds the shortest path $P_{A \rightarrow B}$ from the point **A** to the point **B**, based on the traversal cost (C) of the voxels (v) in \mathbb{G} so that the $\sum v \in P_{A \rightarrow B}$ is the smallest possible cost, while another benefit of D*-lite is the way it saves previous path calculations to speed up the re-planning of P .

The main difference between D*-lite and D_+^* is how \mathbb{G} is constructed from an input map \mathbb{M} . In the proposed scheme, D_+^* is creating \mathbb{G} with the consideration of free, occupied and unknown voxels (v_f, v_o, v_u) and a risk layer. Since the dimensions of \mathbb{G} are changeable, the D_+^* is also able to plan paths in both 2D and 3D. Thus, by creating \mathbb{G} with only one layer in the z -axis it will enable D_+^* to plan a 2D path, while if \mathbb{G} is created with multiple layers in the z -axis it will enable for a 3D path. Because D_+^* is planning P within \mathbb{G} , any path in Fig. 1(a) will be a 2D path and any path in Fig. 1(b) will be a 3D path. Thus, is it possible to use the same algorithm to plan both 2D and 3D paths, where the difference is the map \mathbb{M} from which \mathbb{G} is created.

The proposed D_+^* path planner utilizes three main differences from D*-lite (as presented in Koenig & Likhachev, 2002) namely: (1) the

¹ Link to the code on GitHub: <https://github.com/LTU-RAI/Dsp>.

Fig. 1. \mathbb{G} with one z-layer from a \mathbb{M}_2 and \mathbb{G} with multiple z-layers from a \mathbb{M}_3 . Both \mathbb{M}_2 and \mathbb{M}_3 are created from the same environment.

Fig. 2. A block diagram illustrating how the algorithmic blocks in D_+^* are connected. Algorithm 1 receives updated \mathbb{M} and decides if \mathbb{G} should be created from a scratch (Algorithm 2) or updated (Algorithm 3). Algorithms 4–5 are used as help functions for Algorithms 2–3 to generate risk for \mathbb{G} .

treatment of unknown voxels, (2) proximity risk and (3) map updates. The rest of this Section describes the proposed algorithm in detail, which can be also summarized in Algorithms 1–5. In Fig. 2 a block diagram illustrating how the algorithms in D_+^* are connected with each other is presented, while it should be mentioned that all the implementations are made in C++ within the Robotic Operating System [Stanford Artificial Intelligence Laboratory et al.](#) and are open sourced as indicated before.

2.1. Modeling of unknown space

Imperfections in \mathbb{M} will lead to imperfections in \mathbb{G} that may lead to path short-cutting through walls like the blue path in Fig. 3. In D_+^* this problem is solved by having v_u represented in \mathbb{G} , as well as v_f and v_o . Let C_f, C_u, C_o costs assigned to v_f, v_u, v_o respectively so that $C_f < C_u < C_o$, where in such case P will be planned through v_f instead of v_u even though the resulting P length is longer. This results from the core of D_+^* that plans the path where $\sum \forall C \in P_{A \rightarrow B}$ is the smallest possible. With a higher C_u value the D_+^* will plan the P in v_f at a cost of longer P 's than it would make with a smaller C_u .

2.2. Path planning with a proximity risk

D^* style path planners are created to plan the shortest path from point A to B , and the shortest path around a bend, or corner is to hug, meaning traverse as close as possible inside of the corner of interest. As such, the utilization of such planners introduces the issue that the planned path leaves no room for errors in path following and is even setting limitations to the robot's physical size. To deal with this problematic situation, in D_+^* a risk layer is introduced, where v 's in the proximity of a v_o are given an extra traversal cost C_r and as such the traversal cost of a v in the proximity of a v_o can be defined as:

$$C_r = \begin{cases} \frac{C_u}{d+1} & \text{if } d < r \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3. A comparison of path planning with (red line) and without (blue line) consideration of v_u under the same input \mathbb{M} , starting and endpoint. This comparison does also show the difference between D_+^* and D^* -lite (adjusted for online usage with an octomap). With the utilization of v_u the planned path remains in the caving environment, while without the path it becomes invalid while passing through the solid rock wall.

$$C = \begin{cases} C_f + C_r & \text{if } v \text{ is } v_f \\ C_u + C_r & \text{if } v \text{ is } v_u \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where d is the distance in voxels to the closest v_o and r is the range that is considered as the proximity to a v_o . This novel approach creates a gradient risk that has the highest value next to v_o and decreases with distance as depicted in Fig. 4 where the v with a C_r is depicted.

A direct effect of the proposed D_+^* approach is that in places with sufficient space, this risk layer will enable the planning of a path that is outside of the risk area. However, in the cases where a passage is narrow, the gradient of the risk will cause the path to be planned in

Fig. 5. An illustration of how D_+^* plans a path from the blue ball to the red ball with regards to the risk layer, red voxels are higher risk, green voxels are lower risk, and black voxels are occupied.

Fig. 6. D_+^* outcome in planning a path from A to B in a partially known area where the unknown part is denoted as blue striped. As the robot traverse in the initially planned path, the robot discovers and register more known area and as such the overall path to be executed is online updated.

Fig. 7. Software architecture on Spot.

3.1. 2D path planning: The Boston dynamics spot use case

In this work, the 2D path planning capabilities of D_+^* are tested with the BD Spot robot (see Fig. 8), which is equipped with a 3D lidar, an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), and an onboard computer. The software architecture used is depicted in Fig. 7. In this software configuration, the Google Cartographer (Hess, Kohler, Rapp, & Andor, 2016) was utilized as a Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping (SLAM) algorithm being able to create a 2D grid map M_2 and the corresponding state estimation information. The information from the state estimation uses the current position of the robot, as the starting position A that together with M_2 , and the goal position B are used by D_+^* to plan a

path P. Moreover, a position controller takes P and gives corresponding velocity commands to Spot’s built-in low-level motion controller that makes Spot move. In the experiments with Spot, a prebuild M_2 of the area was provided and thus allowing for a longer, than the sensor range, P to be planned from the beginning of the mission.

A more complete and exhaustive presentation of utilized Spot’s autonomous capability is presented in Koval, Karlsson, and Nikolakopoulos (2022) (see Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Spot equipped with the attached sensors for the autonomy navigation and computational power. In this view perspective, the Vectornav IMU is placed under the Velodyne lidar and is not visible in the Figure.

Fig. 9. The UAV used for the 3D path planning experiments.

Fig. 10. Software architecture on the UAV.

3.2. 3D path planning: the UAV use case

For the 3D path planning experiments, a custom-built UAV was used as depicted in Fig. 9. In this case, the D^*_+ architecture operates in the 3-dimensional space and requires as input the current position A , a goal

position B and an occupancy map M_3 , while it provides the path $P_{A \rightarrow B}$ as an output. The autonomous navigation of the robot is based on the path generated from D^*_+ , which essentially coordinates the motion of the robot, while other modules, such as the state estimation, and a Non-Linear Model Predictive Controller (NMPC) (Lindqvist, Mansouri,

Fig. 11. Sequential **B** were set in a large subterranean tunnel. Spot navigates to each **B** and traverses about 335 m in total. In this experiment, where the map is known a priori, D_4^* shows an increased capability to plan longer paths and excellent replanning capabilities. In this case, B_3 was set before Spot reached B_2 , thus forcing a replanning. When B_3 was reached where a new point B_4 was set at approximately the same point as B_2 .

Fig. 12. Spot navigates along the planned path shown in green, and the traversed path shown in red.

Fig. 13. As Spot traverse the D_+^* planned path from the blue dot to the red dot, more information on the surrounding environment is provided. Thus the planner updates the current \mathbb{M} causing D_+^* to reactively re-plan and adjust the overall path.

Algorithm 5: Calculate C_r when a v is discovered to be free

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1 Input:  $v$ 
2 Output: Updates in  $\mathbb{G}$ 
3  $C_r \leftarrow 0$ 
4 for each  $i$  in  $[-r, r]$  do
5   for each  $j$  in  $[-r, r]$  do
6     for each  $k$  in  $[-r, r]$  do
7        $v_r \leftarrow \mathbb{G}[v_x + i, v_y + j, v_z + k]$ 
8       if  $C_{vr} == C_o$  then
9          $C \leftarrow c_u / (i^2 + j^2 + k^2 + 1)$ 
10        if  $C > C_r$  then
11           $C_r \leftarrow C$ 
12  $\mathbb{G}[v] \leftarrow C_r$ 

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Fig. 14. On the left path planned until the edge of the known map and on the right new path planned towards the goal after a map expansion of the same area. In both cases, the path is denoted by the solid green line.

Haluška & Nikolakopoulos, 2021) that uses an artificial potential field algorithm (Lindqvist, Kanellakis et al., 2021) to reactively avoid obstacles, are part of the overall mission execution. The UAV's primary sensor in the autonomy stack is a Velodyne Puck Lite lidar, which is used alongside an IMU to provide state estimation information on the current position A . In this work, the A is calculated based on LIO-SAM (Shan et al., 2020), while the 3D occupancy map \mathbb{M}_3 is generated based on the Octomap (Hornung et al., 2013) framework.

In these experiments, the artificial potential fields are only used as an extra safety layer to avoid collisions when flying close to obstacles (e.g. less than 50 cm relative distance to an obstacle), where the designed behavior is to prioritize the influence of the potential fields to directly affect the movement since the path, in that case, is

considered to be unsafe. Furthermore, the software architecture for the UAV is visualized in Fig. 10. In all the 3D tests, no information was given a-priori, meaning that the UAV explored \mathcal{M} during the mission, thus utilizing both related map updates and expansions. During the experiments, the waypoints were manually set as the mission was evolving and the desired waypoints were reached, while after some time a waypoint was commanded to set a return to the starting location.

3.3. Graph-based Exploration Planner 2.0

The Graph-based Exploration Planner 2.0 was selected to do a comparison with the proposed method because of its proven capabilities in the DARPA subterranean challenge and the possibility to run it in a waypoint navigation mode, which is similar to how the D_+^* is used. In general, there are considerable differences between Gbplanner and D_+^* , which may bias the evaluation results, depending on the experimental setup. In order to achieve a representative comparison in Gbplanner, the collision model was adjusted to match the UAV size.

4. Experimental results

4.1. 2D path planning

Among the platforms that were used in our experiments, Spot robot has a significantly longer battery life than the UAV and can explore larger subterranean areas. Thus, in this article, the Spot robot was used to evaluate the D_+^* 2D performance. This allowed us to evaluate path planning in larger maps and over longer distances in comparison with the UAV. Worth noting that the computational load for 2D path planning was significantly lower than for 3D. In this case, the experiments with Spot showed that D_+^* is able to plan long paths that were approximately 80m at a time and without collisions. One such experiment, where a multiple waypoint mission was executed, is presented in Fig. 11, where a total of 7 waypoints, were reached progressively. in this case, Spot was capable of navigating to each of the waypoints without collisions.

Another experiment was focusing on the use case where Spot had to traverse approximately 80 m in a more narrow tunnel. Fig. 12 shows how Spot can follow the path planned by D_+^* as it has suitable distances to both walls.

When \mathbb{M} updates it will generate new conditions for D_+^* to plan paths, therefore D_+^* will constantly perform an update of the path to keep it safe. In Fig. 13 it is presented an example of how the path may be re-planned as new information about the environment is acquired. As such, the starting path is planned initially inside a wall but as it is

Fig. 15. Snapshots from three of experiments executed with the UAV.

Fig. 16. D_+ plans a path around a bend while keeping a suitable distance to the inside wall.

Fig. 17. D_+ path planning with a low blockage so that the UAV needs to fly higher to keep a suitable safety marginal to the blockage.

Fig. 18. D_+^* is capable of planning a path from beyond the line of sight to the end of the green line while having the desired safety margin throughout the whole path.

Fig. 19. D_+^* is tasked to plan a path from the red dot to the end of the green line. The resulting path keeps proper safety margins that are relative to the pillar so that the UAV can traverse it safely.

discovered in the corresponding map updates, the path is interfering with a wall and thus reactively D_+^* performs a re-planning of the path to stay away from it and in a safe operation.

Another merit of the proposed D_+^* is the sequential map and graph update capability, which allows planning or re-plan paths towards \mathbb{B} once the robot discovers more parts of the area that navigates along. Fig. 14 depicts the map expansion capability with Spot traversing in the tunnel, wherein the first case the path is planned until the edge of the known map and then a new path is planned in the expanded map of the same area to reach another goal during the mission.

4.2. 3D path planning

D_+^* 3D planning capabilities were also tested in three experiments in a cave tunnel where it was challenged to plan P along (a) a low blockage as depicted in Fig. 15(a), (b) a tall obstacle to the side making a narrow passage as in Fig. 15(b), and (c) around a pillar as depicted in Fig. 15(c).

In the tunnel corner experiment, the D_+^* planned P to follow the bend with a suitable safe marginal to the walls. As shown in Fig. 16 D_+^*

is planning a safe path following the tunnel where only the center point of voxels is selected as waypoints in the path, resulting in a zig-zag path.

D_+^* was also challenged with a low-height obstacle that could potentially risk a collision with the UAV's landing gear if it keeps its current altitude. In this case, P is planned with an altitude change in order to keep the path safe, as depicted in Fig. 17.

At this point, it should be also mentioned that when D_+^* is tasked to plan a path to a point beyond the line of sight, the algorithm is still capable of providing a path that is inherently safe and short as possible. This performance is depicted in Fig. 18 whereas it is shown, the free space gap between the obstacle to the left and the right wall, was very narrow for the UAV to pass through them, and thus a higher path has been selected.

In the last experimental test, the D_+^* is tasked to plan a path from one side of a pillar to the other and then back again. This experiment shows that D_+^* takes the shortest path outside the risky area from the pillar, as also depicted in Fig. 19.

During the experiment, with an obstacle at the side of the tunnel, D_+^* planned P that was in the center of the opening as shown in Fig. 20.

Fig. 20. A UAV avoids colliding with an obstacle on the side by planning P (the green line) in the center of the opening.

Fig. 21. An instance from the autonomous mission and corresponding path planning when the UAV took a too-tight turn around an obstacle and caused the artificial potential field to avoid a collision. The green line is P and the red bars are the path followed by the UAV.

(a) The path D_+^* planned (green) when doing the comparison experiments. The path is as straight as voxel-based planning can be.

(b) The path Gbplanner planned (green) when doing comparison experiments. Note how the path is curving up and around for no apparent reason.

Fig. 22. Differences in planned paths between D_+^* and Gbplanner are visible when both planners plan in the same area under the same conditions.

When passing the obstacle, the remaining planned path converges again to the center of the opening, while keeping a safe distance to all sides.

During all the experimental trials with the UAV, there have been only four times that the potential fields have been triggered to avoid a collision, while two of them were barely noticeable, only just clipping

Fig. 23. The memory consumption of D_+^* and Gbplanner in the comparison experiment. The shaded areas mark the time when D_+^* performed expansion of G .

Fig. 24. The CPU load comparison of D_+^* and Gbplanner in the comparison experiment. The shaded areas mark the time when D_+^* performed expansion of G .

a corner of the protected area, while it should be noted that: (a) the safety would have been guaranteed even without the potential fields, (b) one triggering was because B were set too close to a wall, and (c) the fourth time was during the return on the side obstacle, where P were planned tightly around that. In the final case, the path following had a slightly too long look ahead distance, thus causing it to shortcut the corner in a more intense approach, as it can be seen in Fig. 21. The latest was a dangerous passage close to the obstacle but it was not due to a fault in the D_+^* planner, rather than a weakness in the path following the autonomy stack. In this case, the easiest solution would have been to increase r so P are planned with the proper safe margins for these types of corner-cutting as well.

4.3. Comparison with Graph-based Exploration Planner 2.0

The experiments used for path planners comparison were carried out in the curved subterranean tunnel in Luleå, Sweden. To evaluate their performance the following metrics were used: CPU and memory usage, as well as an assessment of the planned path.

Both planners have been successfully planning a path to traverse the tunnel but the path characteristics differ significantly (see Fig. 22). D_+^* is planning the shortest path from voxel to voxel all the way to the end voxel, resulting in a straight path with no unnecessary detours. Gbplanner on the other hand is an RRT-based planner, which chooses a path leading left and right, up and down to reach a target that is

accessible through a straight line. This approach produces less safe paths, like for example when the path goes close to small objects or walls as it is shown in Fig. 22(b).

Based on our field experience, small structures are not guaranteed to be seen by the mapping algorithm so as a safety feature for the UAV we were using the artificial potential field. It is likely that Gbplanner would have succeeded in any way but the tendency to approach walls and small objects were increasing the risk of collisions. Moreover, these unnecessary movements will reduce UAV's battery life and shorten the maximum distance of the mission.

When we are considering the computational load, the proposed D_+^* is mainly utilizing the CPU for building the graph, which is correlated with the memory usage increases as depicted in Fig. 23 and Fig. 24. During planning and the \mathbb{G} updating, the CPU load is at approximately 10% of a single core. When it comes to resource efficiency, D_+^* is prone to high memory consumption. For example, in the evaluation test, D_+^* used 3.5 – 7.0GB of RAM, while Gbplanner used only 0.2 – 0.3GB of RAM, as shown in Fig. 23. D_+^* capability to replan a path on the fly cannot be compared to Gbplanner because it does not provide an equivalent feature. Some of the differences in performance can be explained by differences in those types of features that in some cases affects the measurable performance (see Fig. 24).

5. Conclusions

In this article, a risk-aware, platform-agnostic path planner called D_+^* has been established. As it was presented, D_+^* utilizes a proximity risk layer to generate a safety margin for any occupied space. The introduced combination of proximity risk and unknown space treatment is able to solve the common issue of shortcuts due to imperfections in the map. By allowing the map to update and expand, the proposed framework is capable of exploring and operating in a previously unknown environment. Finally, the efficiency of the D_+^* has been tested in challenging real-world scenarios with both 2D and 3D planning and it has been proven to reliably plan safe paths in all the evaluated use cases independently of the utilized platform.

Considering large-scale and long-term missions, a potential bottleneck of D_+^* is its computation time when \mathbb{G} is large, and as such future work should aim to improve the computation time for large \mathbb{G} by considering for example map segmentation approaches. Additionally, another point of D_+^* that should be addressed is the severe memory usage. The comparison with Gbplanner showed that it is possible to do memory-efficient path planning that does not require more computation power. This part needs to be investigated and addressed for D_+^* while maintaining the major components of the short straight paths and the dynamic re-planning. The above-mentioned shortcoming in general is related to the resources required to compute P . One direction for lowering memory usage and possibly saving some computation time is to change the data structure of the internal grid map \mathbb{G} . Currently, \mathbb{G} is stored as an array in D_+^* but if it is changed to an oct-tree it is possible that memory usage and computation time can be lowered. Another improvement that can be considered is more types of risks, such as wind or slippery surfaces.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Samuel Karlsson: Conceptualization, Methodology Software, Experiments, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Anton Koval:** Methodology, Experiments, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Christoforos Kanellakis:** Experiments, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **George Nikolakopoulos:** Resources, Experiments, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: George Nikolakopoulos reports financial support was provided by Horizon 2020.

Data availability

The source code is open source at <https://github.com/LTU-RAI/Dsp>.

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